

Northern Mongolian Forest Dynamics Monitoring Using Copernicus Satellite

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Abstract: Mongolian's boreal forests form the southern edge of the Siberian taiga and face increasing pressure from wildfires and logging. This study evaluates forest cover dynamics in northern Mongolia using single-date Sentinel 2 imagery acquired between 2020 and 2025. Forest and non-forest areas, together with dominant forest classes, were mapped using Random Forest classifier to evaluate spatial and temporal patterns of change. Total forest area remained relatively stable during the study period, ranging from 4,987 km² to 5,017 km², which represents 95.7–96.3% of the 5,211.6 km² study area. Among the mapped forest classes, Manchurian birch (*Betula platyphylla*) occupied the largest area (2,060–2,247 km²), followed by Siberian larch (*Larix sibirica*) (1,302–1,455 km²), Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) (567–764 km²), Siberian pine (*Pinus sibirica*) (505–644 km²), and Siberian spruce (*Picea obovata*) (205–294 km²). However, due to spectral overlap among species, these class-specific estimates should be interpreted as indicative rather than definitive. Classification performance was high, with overall accuracy ranging from 0.959 to 0.971 and Kappa values between 0.949 and 0.964. The results indicate that Sentinel-2 imagery is a practical and cost-effective tool for annual forest-cover monitoring in northern Mongolia, although species-level estimates should be interpreted cautiously due to mixed forest stands.

Keywords: Sentinel-2; boreal forests; forest cover change; Random Forest classification; northern Mongolia.

1 Introduction

Comprehensive and spatially explicit information on forest cover is essential for detecting disturbance dynamics, supporting sustainable forest management, and evaluating restoration efforts in boreal ecosystems (Achard et al. 2014, Paquette and Messier 2011). In Mongolia, forest statistics vary widely across national and international sources due to differences in forest definitions, inventory methods, and reporting cycles (FAO 2023, Hansen et al. 2013). These inconsistencies are particularly pronounced in northern Mongolia, where remote terrain, limited accessibility, and frequent wildfires constrain the effectiveness and timely updating of conventional field-based inventories.

Advances in satellite remote sensing and machine learning have enabled large-scale forest monitoring. Multi-temporal Sentinel-2 (ESA) imagery is effective in capturing seasonal spectral variations essential for distinguishing forested and non-forested areas (Fassnacht et al. 2016, Immitzer et al. 2016, Persson et al. 2018). However, classification uncertainties can arise from mixed forest stands, seasonal

variability, and spectral similarity among tree species. Therefore, careful interpretation is needed when assessing species-level forest composition.

This study addresses three main research questions:

- How accurately can forest extent be mapped annually using Sentinel-2 imagery in boreal forests of northern Mongolia?
- What are the spatial and temporal patterns of forest cover change over multiple years, particularly in areas prone to wildfires and other disturbances?
- How reliable and cost-effective is Sentinel-2 data for routine forest monitoring and management in heterogeneous, mixed-species landscapes?

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The study area in northern Mongolia spans parts of Selenge, Darkhan-Uul, and Tuv provinces (Figure 1), covering approximately 5,211.6 km² in the forest-steppe ecotone at the southern edge of the Siberian taiga (Dulamsuren et al. 2010). Forests, occupying 96% of the area, are dominated by Scots pine, Manchurian birch, Siberian larch, and Siberian pine (Environmental Information Center 2025). Wildfires caused most tree cover loss between 2001 and 2024, while forest expansion contributed significantly to national restoration efforts (Global Forest Watch 2024).

2.2 Methods

This study uses multi-source remote sensing and geospatial data to support forest classification and habitat assessment in northern Mongolia, a boreal-temperate forest mosaic important for carbon storage, biodiversity,

Figure 1. Study area: Selenge, Darkhan-Uul, and Tuv provinces.

and ecosystem services (Dulamsuren et al. 2010). Accurate forest mapping and habitat modelling are crucial for sustainable management, conservation, and afforestation planning in the area (Figure 2).

2.2.1 Data Sources and Pre-processing

The study used single-date, cloud-free Sentinel-2 imagery from late summer (August) each year between 2020 and 2025, with one additional June image in 2020. While single annual images do not capture seasonal phenology and may reduce classification robustness, late summer data minimize cloud cover and enhance spectral separation between coniferous and deciduous species. Specific Areas of Interest were delineated for the dominant forest types and non-forested areas. These included: Manchurian birch (54 AOIs), Siberian larch (55 AOIs), Siberian pine (53 AOIs), Scots pine (53 AOIs), Siberian spruce (46 AOIs), and non-forest (52 AOIs). AOIs were selected using the 2019 forest inventory map, high-resolution satellite imagery (Google Earth), and field observations, including only homogeneous stands ≥ 1 ha. However, the non-random, non-stratified selection may limit the spatial representativeness of the training data across the study area. The AOIs guided supervised classification and accuracy validation (Environmental Information Center 2025).

2.2.2 Variable Extraction

Spectral and topographic variables were used for forest classification. Sentinel-2-derived vegetation indices, including NDVI (B8, B4), EVI (B8, B4, B2), GNDVI (B8, B3), NDWI (B3, B8), NDRE (B8, B5), SAVI (B8, B4), MSAVI (B8, B4), NBR (B8, B12), and VARI (B3, B4, B2), captured vegetation condition, chlorophyll content, moisture status, and post-fire recovery, while DEM-derived elevation, slope, and aspect represented terrain-driven variation in species distribution (Barnes et al. 2000, Gao 1996, Gitelson et al. 1995, Huete 1988, Rouse et al. 1974). These variables formed a robust dataset for Random Forest-based forest classification.

2.2.3 Classification Methodology and Evaluation

Forest classification was performed using the Random Forest algorithm (Breiman 2001), an ensemble method suitable for high-dimensional, non-linear data and resistant to overfitting. The model was trained with 70% of the data and tested with 30%, and performance was assessed using Overall Accuracy (OA), Kappa, and F1-score (Congalton and Green 2019).

The model was implemented in R using the *randomForest* package with 500 trees ($n_{tree} = 500$), $m_{try} = 4$ (selected via 5-fold cross-validation), and a minimum node size of 5. Variable importance, measured by mean decrease in Gini impurity, identified NDVI, the near-infrared band (B08), and elevation as the most influential predictors across all years.

3 Results

3.1 Forest tree species classification

Classification results indicate that over 95.7-96.3% of the study area was forested each year, with only minor interannual variations (Figure 3).

Because no mixed-forest class was included, pixels containing multiple species were assigned to a single dominant class. This is particularly important for Manchurian birch and Siberian larch, which frequently co-occur in mixed stands, making clear separation difficult. As a result, apparent year-to-year changes in these two classes should be interpreted with caution, as they most likely reflect classification uncertainty rather than actual ecological change (Table 1).

Manchurian birch shows moderate yearly variation, peaking in 2023 and declining by 2025. Siberian larch slightly decreases after 2022, while Scots pine and Siberian pine gradually increase over the period. Siberian spruce fluctuates, decreasing in 2022 and partially recovering in later years.

Figure 2. Research schema.

Figure 3. Forest tree species classifications (2020-2025).

Table 1. Area of forest tree species (km²).

Year	Manchurian birch	Siberian larch	Scots pine	Siberian pine	Siberian spruce	Total Forest	Non-forested area	Total Area
21-Aug-20	2,207.71	1,396.18	568.99	579.17	261.08	5,013.12	198.48	5,211.6
30-Aug-21	2,099.70	1,451.18	566.85	593.97	294.14	5,005.84	205.76	5,211.6
30-Aug-22	2,214.54	1,454.50	580.81	534.21	205.05	4,989.12	222.48	5,211.6
30-Aug-23	2,246.67	1,396.63	635.77	504.98	233.11	5,017.16	194.44	5,211.6
24-Aug-24	2,168.27	1,306.67	650.26	610.62	264.50	5,000.31	211.29	5,211.6
17-Aug-25	2,059.96	1,302.01	763.97	644.46	217.08	4,987.48	224.12	5,211.6

3.2 Classification evaluation

The classification results, supported by confusion matrices and accuracy metrics, indicate consistently high performance from 2020 to 2025, with overall accuracy ranging from 0.959 to 0.971, Kappa between 0.949 and 0.964, and F1-scores from 0.950 to 0.985 (Figure 4). These metrics demonstrate reliable detection of individual tree species and forest types, although minor fluctuations likely reflect seasonal variations, image quality, and the presence of mixed forest stands, which can reduce class separability. Compared with the 2019 inventory, total forest area derived from Sentinel-2 was lower by 144.08 km² in 2020 and 169.72 km² in 2025. Species-level differences likely

reflect both real changes and classification uncertainty in mixed stands (Table 2). Manchurian birch decreased from 2,773.9 km² (53.8%) in the inventory to 2,059.96 km² (41.2%) in 2025, while Siberian larch increased from 912.3 km² (17.7%) to 1,302.01 km² (26.0%). Scots pine, Siberian pine, and Siberian spruce also show variations between the inventory and Sentinel-2 results, likely reflecting both real forest dynamics and the influence of mixed forest structures on classification. Overall, total forest area remained relatively stable, covering approximately 99.7% of the study area, consistent with the high accuracy metrics observed.

Figure 4. Confusion matrix of forest tree species classification.

Table 2. Forest Cover Changes in northern Mongolia (2019–2025, km²).

Class	Forest Inventory (2019)	Sentinel-2 2020.07.21	Difference (2020)	Sentinel-2 2025.08.17	Difference (2025)
Manchurian birch	2,773.9	2,207.71	-566.19	2,059.96	-713.94
Siberian larch	912.3	1,396.18	483.88	1,302.01	389.71
Scots pine	902.7	568.99	-333.71	763.97	-138.73
Siberian pine	517.4	579.17	61.77	644.46	127.06
Siberian spruce	50.9	261.08	210.18	217.08	166.18
Total	5,157.2	5,013.12		4,987.48	

4 Discussion

The results show that the study area remained consistently forested from 2020 to 2025, with total forest cover exceeding 96%. High classification metrics confirm reliable detection of major forest types, although minor interannual variations likely reflect seasonal differences, image quality, and the presence of mixed forest stands (Immitzer et al. 2016, Zhu et al. 2017). Compared with the 2019 inventory, Manchurian birch decreased while Siberian larch increased, suggesting that both ecological processes and methodological factors, particularly spectral overlap in mixed forests, influence species-level patterns (Dalponte et al. 2012). Overall, Sentinel-2 is effective for mapping general forest cover and dominant vegetation types, but species-level classification is uncertain due to the lack of mixed-forest and sub-pixel

analysis. As a result, estimates for species such as birch and larch contain uncertainties, and temporal trends may partly reflect classification errors rather than real ecological change (Lechner et al. 2020, Lu and Weng 2007). Therefore, the results are suitable for broad forest monitoring but not for precise species-level mapping. Future work should integrate multi-source data (e.g., SAR, LiDAR, hyperspectral) and improved field reference data to enhance classification accuracy (Reiche et al. 2016).

5 Conclusions

The study demonstrates that Sentinel-2 imagery can effectively support annual forest-cover mapping in the boreal forests of northern Mongolia, where total forest cover remained consistently above 96% during the six-year study period. Spatial and temporal analyses indicated

variation among dominant forest classes, including apparent reductions in Manchurian birch and relative increases in Siberian larch, however, these patterns should be interpreted with caution because spectral overlap and mixed species stand may influence class separation. Overall, the findings suggest that Sentinel-2 provides a practical and cost-effective approach for routine forest monitoring, particularly for assessing total forest extent and broad temporal dynamics, while emphasizing the need to account for classification uncertainty in heterogeneous forest landscapes.

6 References

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